

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF WHOLESALE TRADE IN THE ECONOMY

Kholmamatov D.H.

independent researcher of SamIEStute of Economics and Service

Abstract: In the article, the theoretical views of leading scientists on the role and importance of wholesale trade in the country's economy, the main functions performed by wholesale trade, the State Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan UzDT 005:2011 "State Classifier of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The classification of wholesale trade according to the classification of economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2 revisions)" and the classification of international economic activities was studied.

Key words: own account wholesale, fee or contract wholesale, non-specialized wholesale, specialized wholesale, customer-buyer liaison function, customer-supplier liaison function.

INTRODUCTION. Wholesale trade occupies an important place in the system of economic relations between regions of the country, economic sectors, product manufacturers and retail enterprises. Wholesale trade affects regional production, economic relations between industrial sectors, and the system of goods movement. It also affects the improvement of transportation and storage of goods in the country, distribution of regional labor, helps to achieve balance in regional development.

The overall efficiency of the entire economy, the balance of the domestic market, and meeting the growing needs of people are largely related to the activity of wholesale trade. The gradual reduction of monopoly in the commodity and financial markets in the country, the formation of a competitive environment, the reduction of state participation in the economy, and the transition to working on the basis of market mechanisms significantly increase the importance of wholesale trade.

The main reason for the importance of wholesale trade in the economy is that it affects the satisfaction of both the needs of the population and production needs in the consumer market. Therefore, most experts divide wholesale trade into two directions: wholesale trade of finished products and wholesale trade of raw materials and semi-finished products. Wholesale trade of finished products consists of consumer goods, including wholesale trade of non-food products and wholesale trade of food products. Wholesale trade of raw materials and semi-finished products consists of wholesale trade of means of production and wholesale trade of agricultural products sold without processing.

The strengthening of the role of commodity-money relations is connected not only with the development of wholesale trade of consumers, but also with the transition to wholesale trade of means of production. These two forms are becoming the most important channels of planned movement of material, technical and commodity resources.

THE MAIN PART. The role and importance of wholesale trade in the economy is also reflected in the definitions given to it. From the definitions given to most wholesale trade, it can be seen that wholesale trade is interpreted as a type of trade activity related to the purchase and resale of goods in large quantities for business purposes. In particular, according to the international standard for the

classification of all types of economic activity and the state standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "wholesale is the resale (sale without modification) of new or used goods to retailers, production, trade, institutional or professional users or other wholesalers, other persons or companies It is defined as the activity of agents on behalf of buying goods or selling goods to them.

Therefore, the definitions of wholesale trade according to the international classification of economic activities and the classification of economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2 editions) have the same meaning. The definitions given to wholesale trade by specialists who have conducted scientific research related to wholesale trade activity are aimed at revealing the role and importance of this activity in the economy.

A.Koskun Samli and Adel I. from foreign experts on the place and role of wholesale trade in the economy. E.I. Ansari (A. Coskun Samli & Adel I. EI-Ansary) states that wholesale trade plays a major role in ensuring economic growth and developing markets. In their research, based on the experience of economically developed countries, they emphasize that before the introduction of large-scale production, the activity of wholesalers was central in saturating the markets. Another foreign specialist, Hugh MacKeown, provides unique services that help wholesalers save manufacturers from the problems of packaging, packaging, storage and delivery of goods. He also questioned the idea that wholesalers give advances that benefit manufacturers and retailers.

Inadequate development of wholesale trade significantly reduces the efficiency of country commodity markets. This will affect the domestic and foreign markets of domestic producers. Failure to receive information about domestic and foreign markets in time, late response to changes in the external environment, will remove

the movement of goods from your system. The stock of finished products at manufacturers exceeds the norm. This leads to "freezing" of working capital of the enterprise. As a result, it causes serious financial difficulties.

The role and importance of wholesale trade in the economy is reflected in its functions. In a free market, the functions of wholesale trade are important. The main task of wholesale trade is to systematically regulate the supply of products in accordance with the market demand for goods and services. Wholesale trade performs many functions. There is no uniform approach to wholesale functions and their classification. In the scientific studies of many experts, the functions of wholesale trade are divided into two groups: macro-level and micro-level functions (Fig. 1).

The main functions of wholesale trade at the macro level include the functions of integration, evaluation, organization and regulation.

The essence of the integration function of wholesale trade is manifested in the establishment of relations between the participants of the supply and distribution channels of goods, the cooperation of mutual functions, processes, operations.

Figure 1. Functions of wholesale trade

The evaluation function of wholesale trade is related to determining the level of storage, delivery, sales, customer service, necessary labor costs through price mechanisms.

The organizational and regulatory functions of wholesale trade are necessary to ensure the effective organization of the goods movement system and the economic system.

Micro-level wholesale functions cover wholesalers' direct relationships with their trading partners and include:

- conclusion of contracts, their execution;
- conversion of the production range of goods into trade;
- formation of commodity reserves in order to insure the market against changes in the demand for sold goods;
- storage of wholesale purchased goods;
- organization of advisory assistance to the subjects of contractual relations;
- improvement of production with subsequent packing, wrapping, and quality improvement of goods.

In addition to the above, experts suggest that the main functions of wholesale trade should include:

- collection and processing of information about market demand and supply, customers;
- product range formation and purchase function;
- function of storage and storage of products;

transportation function (often wholesalers organize delivery of products for sale to sales locations);

distribution function in the market (wholesale enterprises create the necessary stock of goods, fulfill orders);

the function of moving goods on the market;

supply and sales financing function;

providing consulting services.

The development of wholesale trade in our country is related to the cancellation of the centralized distribution of products in the period after the former totalitarian system, the formation and development of the wholesale trade system that meets modern conditions.

In our opinion, the organization and management mechanism of wholesale trade is also very important. Today, wholesale activity is organized in several forms and forms. Enterprises engaged in wholesale trade differ according to their organizational and legal status, form of ownership, scope of activity and independence. Scientific literature also mentions a number of types of wholesalers.

Foreign experts classify wholesalers as follows (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Types of wholesalers.

O'zDT 005:2011 State standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan "State classifier of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The classification of entities engaged in wholesale trade is presented in section G "Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles" of the economic activity classification of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2 revisions). According to him, wholesale trade enterprises, that is, wholesalers who take ownership of the goods they sell; wholesalers, brokers, wholesale trade enterprises specializing in providing services to the industry; mining enterprises include the main types of commercial enterprises, such as exporters, importers, cooperative associations, branches and sales bureaus, whose duties are not limited to taking orders directly from factories or mines, which hold their products for sale. Also included are middlemen and agents engaged in the sale of agricultural products, producers and cooperative associations.

O'zDT 005:2011 State standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan "State classifier of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Classifier of economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2 editions)" G "Wholesale and retail trade; Section 45 "wholesale and retail sale of automobiles and motorcycles and their repair" and section 46 "wholesale trade other than sale of automobiles and motorcycles" of section 45 "repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles" provide a complete classification of wholesale trade activities. Section 46 covers wholesaling on own account or under contract (commission trading), including domestic wholesaling, as well as international wholesaling (import/export).

According to the classification of international economic activities, Hamulgurji trade activities are fully classified in 46 sections, 461-469 groups and classes.

Figure 3. Classification of commercial activities according to the International Economic Activity Classification Standard

In a number of scientific studies, the development of wholesale trade in the economy is shown to be related to its stages. Wholesale trade consists of 4 stages according to the state of development in the economy (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Stages of development of wholesale trade

CONCLUSION. In Uzbekistan, the role and importance of wholesale trade in deep processing of local raw materials resources, increasing the production of import substitute products, diversification in the industry, ensuring further saturation of the consumer market is increasing significantly. In addition, it should be noted that wholesale trade affects the improvement of the quality of local goods and serves to establish a firm footing of goods in both domestic and foreign markets.

Thus, wholesale trade enterprises organize the establishment of economic relations and exchange of goods between manufacturers of goods, retail trade enterprises, intermediary enterprises and other buyers. The main indicator of the development of wholesale trade is the need of production enterprises for raw materials, semi-finished products, spare parts, components and other means of production, the demand for consumer goods and the level of purchasing power of the population. Growth of wholesale turnover, as well as purchasing choices in consumer behavior from the point of view of marketing, demand formation and sales promotion activities, stages of the life cycle of goods, logistics service: ensuring adequate stock of goods, timely delivery of goods in the right amount to the right place, It is also related to after-sales service.

List of used literature

1. International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities. Revision 4. ST/ESA/STAT/SER.M/4/Rev.4
2. Coskun Samli & Adel I. EI-Ansary (2007). The role of wholesalers in developing countries. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research Journal, vol. 17, pp. 353-358

3. Hugh MacKeown (2007) Wholesaling and wholesaling research: A practitioner's viewpoint. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research Journal*, vol. 17, pp. 413-422
4. State classifier of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Classification of economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2 revisions) – O'zDT 005:2011
5. Philip Kotler. *Marketing essentials*. Prentice-Hall, 1984. 556 pages.